

Information sheet 1.17 - Post-entry quarantine and other restrictions of movement in the importing country

This information sheet covers post-entry quarantine (PEQ) of relevant commodities; temporal, spatial and end-use restrictions in the importing country for import of relevant commodities; Prohibition of import of relevant commodities into the domestic country. 'Relevant commodities' are plants, plant parts and other materials that may carry pests, either as infection, infestation, or contamination.

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Jeger M, Bragard C, Caffier D, Candresse T, Chatzivassiliou E, Dehnen-Schmutz K, Grégoire J-C, Jaques Miret JA, MacLeod A, Navajas Navarro M, Niere B, Parnell S, Potting R, Rafoss T, Rossi V, Urek G, Van Bruggen A, Van der Werf W, West J, Winter S, Hart A, Schans J, Schrader G, Suffert M, Kertész V, Kozelska S, Mannino MR, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S, Vos S and Gilioli G, 2018. Guidance of the EFSA PLH Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment. *EFSA Journal* 2018;16(7):5350, 94 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350. Available online at <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350>

This document is currently still under preparation and will be made available in the near future.